

Research

The Anti-Inflammatory Effects of Nonsteroidal Drugs and Aspirin in Colon Cancer

Sami Ul Haq Niazi¹, XinYu Hu², Professor Dong Xia^{3*}

Department of Gastrointestinal surgery, The Affiliated Hospital of Southwest Medical University, Luzhou 646000, Sichuan Province, People's Republic Of China;

*Corresponding author

Professor Dong Xia

xdcndoc@126.com

Accepted: 10 December, 2020; Online: 23 December, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4391438>

Abstract: the findings strongly, if not conclusively, indicate that on the proliferation of colon cells in culture the effect of some Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), and on the two contributing parameters of cell proliferation, i.e., apoptosis and cell cycle, is exerted independent of their inhibitory effect on PG synthesis. A mechanism unrelated to inhibition of apoptosis in response to Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and PG synthesis that affects the cell cycle phase distribution is currently being sought.

Keywords: Colon Cancer , apoptotic cells, Adenocarcinoma , Polyps

INTRODUCTION

Colon is the last part of human digestive tract and the cancer of this part is called Colon Cancer. Most of the cases related to colon cancer start with small, noncancerous clumps (benign) named adenomatous polyps (Cappell, 2008). Some of such polyps gradually can transform into colon cancer. Polyps can be tiny and symptomatic. That are the reason practitioners emphasize time to time screening tests to identify and then remove polyps as a measure to help prevent cancer (Cappell, 2005).

Symptoms and signs of the colon cancer may include: bleeding with stool or rectal bleeding, constipation of diarrhea or any change in bowel routines and its consistency in stool lasting longer than 28 days, gas, pain or cramps or any persistent abdominal uneasiness, fatigue and weakness, feeling the bowel not emptying completely and unintelligible weight loss. Generally, after the age of 50 colon cancer screening is a must in case of any abdominal discomfort. In most of the cases, the causes of colon cancer are ambiguous. Colons cancer, however, occur when there are some errors in the DNA of the healthy colon cells. Although much of the causes are not clear yet a series of evidences has indicated that lifestyle and dietary factors have much to do with the colon cancer risk (Cummings *et al.*, 1992). Lack of physical activity, adiposity deposition and excessive weight are some consistent and common risk factors. In Europe and USA, the key contributor to most of colon cancers is overconsumption of energy. Role of some macronutrients, apart from the impact of energy equilibrium, have remained controversial. Processed meat refined or processed carbohydrates and red meat also contribute to cancer risk. Some studies have found that chronic hyperinsulinemia can also scale up the risk factor as hyperinsulinemia help increase IGI-1 experience. Excessive alcoholism with low use of micronutrients coupled with smoking in childhood may increase the risk factors. Insulin resistance and diabetic patients tends to have increased risks of cancer (Thune and Furberg, 2001). Among all the races and ethnicities, African-Americans fall prey to colon cancer more than any other race or ethnicity. Each year almost 160,000 people were diagnosed with colorectal cancer and in North Americas colorectal adenocarcinoma is the most common cancer and the second leading cause of death in the USA. Annually approximately 60,000 people died from colorectal cancer (Steele, 1994). In economically developed countries cancer of the colorectum is the most common malignancies but by lifestyle modification and dietary modifications majority of the malignancies are preventable (Giovannucci, 1999).

The non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) which are sulindac, aspirin, piroxicam and indomethacin in rodents inhibit the colon cancer's growth which was induced by the carcinogens chemical (Gridley *et al.*, 1994; Giovannucci *et al.*, 1993; Waddell and Loughry, 1983; Giardiello *et al.*, 1993; Reddy *et al.*, 1993; Pollard and Luckert, 1981; Moorghen *et al.*, 1988; Pollard *et al.*, 1983; Vane and Botting, 2003; Vargaftig and Lefort, 1997; Humes *et al.*, 1981; Ferreira, 1977;

Hanif *et al.*, 1996). The major mechanism of action of the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) is the inhibition of cyclo-oxygenase and the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs

(NSAIDs) are belong to the family of pharmacological compounds. Cyclo-oxygenase is a key enzyme which is useful in the conversion of arachidonic acid to eicosanoids (Vane, 1971). From a variety of chemical classes, twelve additional non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are prescribed in the USA in addition to non-acetylated salicylates and aspirin (Brooks and Day, 1991). These agents are used to exhibit the anti-pyretic activity, analgesic and anti-inflammatory activity.

Arachidonic acid is derived through the linoleic acid modification or through diet. Through the cytochrome P450 enzymes, cyclo-oxygenase pathway and the lipoxygenase pathway arachidonic acid is metabolized. Primarily, by inhibiting the enzyme activity of cyclo-oxygenase which is also known as prostaglandin H synthase and the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) were interrupt the pathway of cyclo-oxygenase and consequently the synthesis of prostaglandin decreases and other generated eicosanoids by the cyclo-oxygenase action. In general, however, to suppress the inflammation and the dosage of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) is required and in the plasma the increased doses may subsequently do necessary for this suppression, suggesting that through unidentified additional mechanisms these drugs work through it (Brooks and Day, 1991).

In humans there are two enzymes of cyclo-oxygenase present which are cyclo-oxygenase-1 (COX-

1) and cyclo-oxygenase-2 (COX-2) (also known as prostaglandin H synthase, prostaglandin endoperoxide synthase and prostaglandin G/H synthase). The sensitivity of cyclo-oxygenase-2 (COX-2) has different than to cyclo-oxygenase (COX-1) to the inhibition of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) (Dubois *et al.*, 1998). Non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) have variety of other factors effects in addition to the prostaglandin synthesis inhibition. These effects include the inhibition of the function of neutrophil retardation (such as

the unmasking of the T-cell suppressor activity, cell-cell aggregation and the phospholipase C production activity interference) and lipoxygenase enzymes (Brooks and Day, 1971).

Aspirin is also known as acetylsalicylic acid (ASA) and it is a medication which was from last ten years used for its anti-inflammatory properties. Acetylsalicylic acid (ASA) was first introduced by Bayer in 1899 into the market and it was registered under the name of “Aspirin”. Although many indications have been seen for acetylsalicylic acid (ASA) and recently it has the potential role in the colorectal cancer prevention (Thun *et al.*, 1991). Aspirin or acetylsalicylic acid is belonging as a family member of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) and works by inhibiting cyclooxygenase-1 (COX-1). The production of thromboxane A₂ is reduced by the inhibition of COX-1 which eventually leads to the downstream inhibition of platelet aggregation. Acetylsalicylic acid (ASA) has been shown to reduce the production of prostaglandins which is also implicated by the COX-1 and COX-2 pathways. In addition of their traditional function, prostaglandins have been associated with reduced immune surveillance of cancer cells, cell proliferation, less apoptosis and tumour angiogenesis (Dannenberg *et al.*, 2005). Through various pathways this occurs, through signalling of phosphatidylinositol 3-kinase (PI3K) which has been specifically studied in colorectal cancer (Liao *et al.*, 2012).

The first observational evidence that is favouring aspirin was came from the case control study of Melbourne which revealed that in non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) users a 42% reduction in the risk of colorectal cancer was observed (Kune *et al.*, 2007). Kune and his colleagues in 1988 reported an inverse relationship between the risk for colorectal cancer and the use of aspirin

(Kune *et al.*, 1988). In the models of experimentally induced colon cancer, the nonsteroidal drugs anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) are the agents which are chemo-preventive rule (Gridley *et al.*, 1994; Giovannucci *et al.*, 1993; Waddell and Loughry, 1983; Giardiello *et al.*, 1993; Reddy *et al.*, 1993; Pollard and Luckert, 1981; Moorghen *et al.*, 1988; Pollard *et al.*, 1983; Vane and Botting, 2003; Vargaftig and Lefort, 1997; Humes *et al.*, 1981; Ferreira, 1977; Hanif *et al.*, 1996). The evidences of epidemiological studies have significantly showed that the people who have taken the non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs or aspirin are at a reduced risk of developing the

colon cancer and at reduced risk of dying from the colon cancer (Gridley *et al.*, 1993; Giovannucci *et al.*, 1994).

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY

Area of Research

Research was conducted in a comprehensive search of literature database was undertaken including but not limited to Pubmed, Ovid, Embase and Wiley from oct 2019 to march 2020. All potential studies were identified and lists of citations were made for removal of duplicate studies. Colon Cancer “risk factors” genetic Risk factors, Influence Factors and process was carried out. A variety of keywords has been used ,apoptotic cells, Adenocarcinoma, constipation, Polyps ,Non-steroids and so.

After the removal of duplicate studies abstract assessment was carried out. Irrelevant studies were removed and final list including the final review. Studies concerning factors for colon cancer were considered eligible and there were no language restriction imposed. And the analysis was done in _____.

Sample Size

100 patients of both male and female were taken and were selected out of on randomized basis. The sociodemographic data was collected which includes the medical and sociodemographic of the participant. After that, to check the effect of this study NSAIDs were given to both male and female subjects. Zero sampling was done before start of research trails.

Cell Lines

Cell lines HCT-15 (ATCC CCL 225) and HT-29 (ATCC HTB 38) of the human colon adenocarcinoma from the American Type Culture Collection were obtained (ATCC, Rockville, MD). HCT-15 cells were cultured in RPMI 1640 and HT-29 cells in McCoy's 5A medium. These mediums were supplemented with penicillin (50U/mL), 10% FBS (Gemini Bioproducts, Inc., Calabasas, CA), streptomycin (50µg/mL) and non-essential amino acids (all from Life Technologies, Inc., Gaithersburg, MD). Cells were incubated in 5% CO₂ at 37°, were grown as monolayers in P100 plates and in 90% relative humidity.

Reagent

PGs (Sigma), Piroxicam (Sigma Chemical Co., St. Louis, MO) and Sulindac sulfide (desoxy-sulindac, provided by Merck and Co., Rahway, NJ) were dissolved in DMSO (Fisher Scientific, Fair Lawn, NJ). To prevent oxidation after each use nitrogen was passed over the PG solution. In all the media the concentration of DMSO was adjusted to be equal. PGI₂, A23187, PGE₂, arachidonic acid, mellitin and PGF₂ α (all from sigma) were dissolved in DMSO and stored at -20°.

Levels of Eicosanoid

By the radioimmunoassay in the culture media eicosanoid levels were determined directly (Rigas and Levine, 1983; Levine, 1986). The supernatant was frozen at -20° and to pellet floating cell the samples of culture media were centrifuged at 500 g at 4° until the eicosanoid levels were determined.

Cell Cycle Analysis and Cell Proliferation

From monolayers of cells single cell suspensions were obtained as follow. First, with PBS pH 7.2 cells were washed, with 1% BSA (PBS/BSA) cells were supplemented and then with Trypsin EDTA (Life Technologies, Inc., Grand Island, NY) cells were incubated. Then in the presence of PBS/BSA from the dish's cells were collected. In the culture medium by low-speed centrifugation floating cells were harvested and with the adherent cell fraction pooled. In 1 mL of PBS/BSA cells were resuspended and washed. By using a hemacytometer Aliquots of cells were counted.

For the analysis of cell cycle, with 70% ice-cold ethanol cells were fixed, for minimum of 30 minutes cells were incubated at -20°, then for 5 minutes treated with 0.1% NP-40 on ice and with PBS/BSA the cells were washed. Next in 200 μ g/mL RNase type IIA (Sigma) and in 40 μ g/mL propidium iodide (Sigma) cells were resuspended in PBS/BSA and by using a Coulter ELITE flow cytometer cells were incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature prior to measuring their content of DNA. To assist in data analysis and to generate the frequency histograms of DNA content the MULTICYCLE AV software program (Phoenix Flow Systems, San Diego, CA) was used.

Apoptosis

For evidence of apoptosis cells were evaluated by three different assays: (a) by propidium iodide staining measurement of the content of DNA and to detect the changes flow cytometric analysis was used that is associated with the fragmentation of DNA during the occurring of apoptosis

(Elstein and Zucker, 1994; Darzynkiewicz *et al.*, 1992). (b) to identify the characteristics and cellular morphological changes of apoptosis by acridine orange staining (Darzynkiewicz, 1990) and (c) to detect the degradation of DNA associated with apoptosis by agarose gel electrophoresis of genomic DNA (Wyllie, 1980).

Acridine Orange Staining

From drug treated or control dishes 50,000 freshly harvested cells for fluorescence microscopy were applied to glass slides for 5 minutes in cytospin well by centrifugation at 700 g (Cytospin 2, Shandon Inc., Pittsburgh, PA). For at least 20 minutes these slides in acetic acid:ethanol (1:9, v/v) were fixed by immersion. For 1 minute these slides upon drying were washed with HBSS treated with 0.1 % Triton ice-cold X-100/0.08 N HCl/0.15 M NaCl for 1 minute and stained in a buffer of phosphate-citric acid (pH 6) containing 0.15 M NaCl and 1 mM EDTA with 20 μ M acridine orange (Sigma). Another wash following with HBSS, with the help of cover slips the slides were covered and under photographed (Nikon Inc., Labophot, Melville, NY) and fluorescence microscopy cells were examined. To quantify the apoptotic cells fraction, the morphological criteria used on these slides included the presence of (a) nuclear shrinkage and cytoplasmic (b) condensation of chromatin; and (c) Zeiosis (with the maintenance of cell membrane integrity, cytoplasmic blebbing) (Cohen, 1993). On the slide among all of the cells present the percentage of apoptotic cells was determined by selected randomly counting ten high-power fields.

DNA Degradation

At a density of 10×10^6 cells/dish cells were plated and for 48 hours cells were treated with drug-supplemented or control medium. From 4.5×10^6 HCT-15 cells genomic DNA was obtained by lysis in 1mM EDTA/0.04 M Tris-acetate/0.25% NP-40. For 1 hour with 100 μ g/mL boiled RNase AI (Sigma) these extracts were digested at 37° followed by the proteinase K (Boehringer-Mannheim, Indianapolis, IN) for 18 hours at 37° at a concentration of 1mg/mL. From the equivalent of 1×10^6 cells aliquots of DNA were mixed with the buffer sample (final concentration: bromophenol blue 0.025% $\pm$ 0.025% xylene cyanol/glycerol 3.0%) and with impregnated ethidium bromide (0.1 μ g/mL) resolved in 1.8% agarose gels. By photographed and UV transillumination DNA was visualized by using 667 Polaroid film.

RT-PCR

To identify mRNA in the HCT-15 and HT-29 cells for COX-2 and COX-1, based on the RT-PCR analytical procedure the exact primers were synthesized that are developed for human cyclooxygenases (Hla and Neilson, 1992; Funk and FitzGerald, 1991). The primers for human COX-1 were 5'-GTGCATCAACACAGGCGCCTCTTC-3' (at 819 position, a 24-mer antisense oligonucleotide) and 5'-TGCCCAGCTCCTGGCCCCGCCGCTT-3' (at 516 position, a 24-mer sense oligonucleotide), giving rise to a PCR product 303 bp (Hla and Neilson, 1992; Funk *et al.*, 1991). The primers for human COX-2 were 5'-AGATCATCTCTGCCTGAGTATCTT-3' (at 878 position, 24-mer antisense oligonucleotide) and 5'-TTCAAATGAGATTGTGGGAAAATTGCT-3' (at 573 position, a 27-mer sense oligonucleotide), giving rise to a PCR product 305 bp. From cultured HCT-15 and HT-29 cells equal quantities of mRNA i.e. 500 ng were amplified, and reverse transcribed by using an RT-PCR kit (Perkin-Elmer Cetus, Norwalk, CT) by following the manufacturer's instructions. Using a cycling program of 94°, for 40 cycles PCR was performed for 1 minute, 72° for 1 minute and 55° for 1 minute in a 2 GCT-1 Precision Scientific Thermal Cycler. The actin mRNA, as a control was also amplified and reverse transcribed, using the following primers: 5'-GTGGCCATCTCCTGCTCGAAGTC-3' (at 727 position, a 23-mer oligonucleotide) and 5'-GTTTGAGACCTTCAACACCCC-3' (at 409 position, a 21-mer sense oligonucleotide), giving rise to a PCR product 318 bp. At 94° using a cyclic program, 35 cycles of PCR were performed for 1 minute, 72° for 1 minute and 60° for 1 minute. By electrophoresis, an aliquot of reaction mixture following the amplification was fractionated in a 2% agarose gel.

Statistical Analysis

At least three times all the experiments were repeat and similar results were obtained. For statistical analysis unpaired t-tests were used. The results were considered significant when the value of $P < 0.05$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Production of PG by HT-29 and HCT-15 Colon Adenocarcinoma Cells

Production of PG profile was determined by HT-29 and HCT-15 cells. In P100 petri dish cells (1×10^6) were plated for 24 hours in the presence of FBS at which time three times the cells were washed with PBS which is prewarmed and once with the medium that is without FBS. In culture medium then the cells were incubated either without or with the supplementation with FBS. The culture medium was harvested after another 24 hours and the PGs were assayed. As it is shown

in Table 1, that HT-29 cells produced PGF2 α (0.011 $\pm$ 0.006 ng/mL), PGI2 (0.022 $\pm$ 0.010 ng/mL) and PGE2 (0.052 $\pm$ 0.009 ng/mL; mean $\pm$ SEM) whereas HCT-15 cells did not produce any PGs cell in the absence of FBS. TxA2 was not capably produced neither by cell line appearance, then TxA2 was assayed as its product which is TxB2. The culture medium in the presence of serum when either the cell line was cultured, both contained PGs. The PGF2 α and PGE2 that were detected in case of HCT-15 cells originated from the FBS that was added to the medium. The increased amounts of PGs in case of HT-29 cells present in FBS, appeared to result from the exogenously added PGF2 α and PGE2 and also from the production of endogenous PG which was stimulated by the serum. In media supplemented with FBS, similar amounts of PGs were present, but not incubated with the cells, whereas in media which is not supplemented with FBS, no amounts of PGs were present.

TABLE 1. Levels of PG in the medium when the cells of HT-29 or HCT-15 were cultured for 24 hours without or with FESS

Prostaglandins (ng/mL)				
Cell Line	PGE2	PGF2α	PGI2	TxA2*
HT-29				
(-) FBS	0.052 $\pm$ 0.009	0.011 $\pm$ 0.006	0.022 $\pm$ 0.010	undetectable
(+) FBS	0.459 $\pm$ 0.010	0.076 $\pm$ 0.007	0.067 $\pm$ 0.003	not determined
HCT-15				
(-) FBS	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable
(+) FBS	0.050 $\pm$ 0.012	0.030 $\pm$ 0.006	undetectable	not determined

From three independent assays, the values are mean $\pm$ SEM

*As its product TxA2 was assayed, TxB2

PGs do not produce by the HCT-15 cells, was further confirmed by treating these cells with three known potent stimulators of PG synthesis either mellitin, arachidonic acid and A23187 (Cole *et al.*, 1986; Hassid and Levine, 1977; Hong *et al.*, 1976). In the presence of FBS, HT-29 and HCT-15 were plated, 24 hours prior to the experiment. Then with prewarmed PBS three times the cells were washed and once with medium without FBS. With medium containing mellitin (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) or arachidonic acid (1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) or A23187 (0.01 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), this was followed without FBS by incubation for 30 min. In the culture media, PGs were then assayed. By producing increased amounts of the PGs, HT-29 cells as expected, responded to stimulation (over the baseline 3 to 5-fold increases) whereas, HCT-15 cells did not produce any PGs.

FIG. 2. Effects of PGE₂ and sulindac sulfide on cell proliferation in HCT-15 cells. The cells were cultured in the presence of FBS and counted at 24, 48, and 72 hr. Each value represents the mean $\pm$ SEM (N = 4). SS = sulindac sulfide.

On the Anti-proliferative Activity of Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs), effect of PGs on Colon Cancer Cells

At a density of 0.75×10^6 HT-29 and HCT-15 cells in 100 tissue culture dishes were plated. Since with 10% FBS, in culture beyond 24 hours, FBS needed by cells to be sustained, all the media were supplemented in which small amounts of PGs is present. Under study, 24 hours after plating, cells were incubated with the appropriate PG and with the Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). Every day media was changed along with addition of fresh

compounds. After the addition of the test compounds cells were harvested 72, 24 and 48 hours. As predictable, the number of HCT-15 cells reduced by sulindac sulfide (200 FM) which is shown in Figure. 2; after its addition to the culture medium as early as 24 hours this effect became evident. On the proliferation rate of HCT-15 cells at 10^{-6} or 10^{-8} M concomitant administration of PGE, did not reverse the effect of sulindac sulfide. Prior to adding sulindac sulfide for 24 hours, with PGE2 the treatment of cells, did not prevent the antiproliferative effect of sulindac sulfide. Similarly, over the same range of concentrations PGF2 α applied, also failed on the proliferation rate of HCT- 15 cells to reverse the effect of sulindac sulfide, when studied for 72 hours. Simultaneous at a concentration of 10^{-10} M addition of PGF2 α and PGE2, on the proliferation of cell also did not reverse the effect of sulindac sulfide. Of note, over control cells at 72 hours (P = 0.032) by 25% both PGF2 α and PGE2, by themselves stimulated the rate of proliferation of these cells. This finding showed that both the PGF2 α and PGE2 provides an important control, indicating that to the culture media they were added were biologically active. In HT-29 cells, similar changes were observed. As early as 24 hours, the rate of proliferation of HT-29 cells suppressed after the addition of Sulindac sulfide (185 μ M) to the medium.

Figure. 2. In HCT-15 cells, effects of Sulindac Sulphide and PGE2 on Cell Proliferation
**Effect of PGs on Changes induced by Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) on
the Cell Cycle Distribution**

From the experiments described above, aliquots of cell cultures were obtained and in the phases of the cell cycle by flow cytometric analysis their distribution was determined. At incubated for up to 72 hours and in the presence of FBS when the HCT-15 cells were grown, the Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) in their cell cycle distribution induced significant changes. Within 24 hours of treatment a G2/M arrest with Sulindac sulfide induced which continued into 48 hours. On the DNA frequency, this was associated as a subdiploid peak with apoptosis detectable. At a concentration of 10^{-6} or 10^{-8} M, addition of PGE2 or PGF2 α simultaneously with either piroxicam or sulindac sulfide failed to prevent these changes. In the cell cycle distribution these PGs of HCT-15 cells did not produce any significant changes by themselves. With 185 μ M sulindac sulfide the treatment of HT-29 cells (the same protocol following as for HCT-15 cells) in their cell cycle distribution led to significant changes. A G1 arrest induced by Sulindac sulfide in these cells as opposed in the HCT-15 cells the G2 arrest was observed. After 72 hours of treatment apoptosis in the form of a subdiploid peak with sulindac sulfide, also became evident.

To Reserve the Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory Drugs (NSAIDs) Induced Apoptosis, failure of PGs in Colon Cancer Cell Lines

In the cell line of colon cancer, in the HT-29 cells the Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) induce apoptosis (Shiff *et al.*, 1995; Shiff *et al.*, 1996). In HCT-15 cells, a similar phenomenon was observed, and it was examined whether by Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) the inhibition of PG synthesis was dependent on this effect. In parallel experiments apoptosis was evaluated by (a) after staining the cells with acridine orange, evaluating the cellular morphology (b) by flow cytometric analysis, assessing the DNA degradation and (c) by agarose gel electrophoresis examining the genomic DNA degradation. For up to 72 hours, when these two cell lines were studied in both HT-29 and HCT-15 cells, at 200 μ M sulindac sulfide induced apoptosis. In Table 2, as summarized, in HT-29 cells, as assessed by acridine orange staining, the apoptosis at 24 hr, 48 hr and at 72 hr induced by sulindac sulfide was 5%, 7% and 23% respectively. In HCT-15 cells as assessed by acridine orange staining, the apoptosis at 24 hr, 48 hr and at 72 hr induced by sulindac sulfide was 13%, 42% and 44% respectively (Table 2). Similar changes were indicated by flow cytometric (Table 2). Simultaneously at 10^{-6} , 10^{-8} , or 10^{-

10^{-10} M, the addition of PGF 2α or PGE 2 with sulindac sulfide did not reverse this effect. There was no effect on apoptosis when PGs were added alone to the cells, as assessed by either method. Finally, in response to sulindac sulfide treatment a hallmark of apoptosis, the genomic DNA degradation, was also analysed by size fractioning the genomic DNA of HCT- 15 cells.

TABLE 2. In HT-29 or HCT-15 effect of PGE2 on apoptosis induced by sulindac sulfide

	Flow Cytometry*			Acridine Orange+		
	24 hr	48 hr	72 hr	24 hr	48 hr	72 hr
HT-29						
Control	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable
Sulindac sulphide (SS)	undetectable	undetectable	45	5	7	23
PGE2 +SS (10 ⁻⁶ M)	undetectable	undetectable	38	5	6	20
PGE2 +SS (10 ⁻⁸ M)	undetectable	undetectable	42	4	7	25
PGE2 10 ⁻⁶ M	undetectable	undetectable		undetectable	undetectable	undetectable
PGE2 10 ⁻⁸ M	undetectable	undetectable		undetectable	undetectable	undetectable

HCT-15						
Control	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable	2	1	1
Sulindac sulphide (SS)	7	33	27	13	42	44
PGE2 +SS (10 ⁻⁶ M)	12	34	43	14	52	55
PGE2 +SS (10 ⁻⁸ M)	8	27	29	10	51	54
PGE2 10 ⁻⁶ M	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable	3	2	3
PGE2 10 ⁻⁸ M	undetectable	undetectable	undetectable	3	0.5	undetectable

* When analysed by flow cytometry, percent of cells exhibiting a subdiploid peak of DNA. + When stained with acridine orange, percent of cells exhibiting morphological changes characteristic of apoptosis.

Discussion

The findings explain that the rate of proliferation of two colon adenocarcinoma cell lines Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), piroxicam and sulindac sulfide inhibited by a mechanism to inhibit PG synthesis independent of their ability. This conclusion supported by two lines of evidence: (a) in cells that produce PGs the same effect occurred as in cells that do not, and

(b) the effect of Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) did not reverse by exogenously added PGs. The HCT-15 and HT-29 cell lines, differed in their ability to produce PGs; the former produced PGs but the latter did not. The HT-29 cells, which constitutively synthesized three PGs, this is in contrast to when HCT-15 cells, their media contained no detectable PGs were cultured in the absence of serum. on the biosynthetic profile of these cell lines these findings are consistent with previous reports with respect to PGs (Hubbard *et al.*, 1991). The conclusion was further strengthened by two observations: (a) three different PG synthesis potent stimulators by the HCT-15 cells failed to induce PG production, while by the HT-29 cells, stimulating the PG production and (b) in HCT-15 cells transcripts of the two known cyclooxygenase genes, COX-2 and COX-1, were not detectable, while in HT-29 cells they were present.

In this study, the Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) used belong to different chemical classes: piroxicam of the “enolic acid group” and sulindac sulfide is a member of the

“acetic acid group”. These findings, therefore, argue against an effect restricted to a single compound, and that the conclusion may apply to many and raise the possibility, if not all, Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs). The findings that in vitro as well as two contributing

parameters apoptosis and cell cycle distribution, the Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) can affect the rate of proliferation of colon adenocarcinoma cells, by a mechanism other than inhibition of PG synthesis, is not totally unexpected. Over the last several years, that the mechanism of some of the actions of Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) is not related to their ability to inhibit PG synthesis and for this purpose evidence has been accumulating. For example, the required dose for their anti-inflammatory effect to inhibit the cyclooxygenase is greater than the doses of Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) required are much lower (Flower *et al.*, 1980) Sodium salicylate does not inhibit cyclooxygenase in addition, to the Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) at the concentrations used clinically, but it still is an effective anti-inflammatory agent. In addition, via a PG-independent mechanism, sodium salicylate and aspirin inhibit an inducible eukaryotic transcription factor of the Rel family and the activation of NF- κ B (Grilli *et al.*, 1993), which therefore inactivates certain genes involved in the immune and inflammatory response (Kopp and Ghosh, 1994). Finally, to the present study two observations have been made that directly relate: (a) in human fibroblasts by Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) PGs do not prevent growth inhibition (Hial *et al.*, 1977).

In summary, the findings strongly, if not conclusively, indicate that on the proliferation of colon cells in culture the effect of some Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), and on the two contributing parameters of cell proliferation, i.e., apoptosis and cell cycle, is exerted independent of their inhibitory effect on PG synthesis. A mechanism unrelated to inhibition of apoptosis in response to Non-steroidal Anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and PG synthesis that affects the cell cycle phase distribution is currently being sought.

References

- Brooks, P. M., & Day, R. O. (1991). Nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drugs—differences and similarities. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 324(24), 1716-1725.
- Cappell, M. S. (2005). The pathophysiology, clinical presentation, and diagnosis of colon cancer and adenomatous polyps. *Medical Clinics*, 89(1), 1-42.
- Cappell, M. S. (2008). Pathophysiology, clinical presentation, and management of colon cancer. *Gastroenterology Clinics of North America*, 37(1), 1-24.
- Cohen, J., (1993). Apoptosis. *Immunology Today*, 14(1): 126-130.
- Cole, O. F., Fan, T. P., & Lewis, G. P. (1986). Release of eicosamoids from cultured rat aortic endothelial cells; studies with arachidonic acid and calcium ionophore A23187. *Cell biology international reports*, 10(6), 407-413.
- Cummings, J. H., Bingham, S. A., Heaton, K. W., & Eastwood, M. A. (1992). Fecal weight, colon cancer risk, and dietary intake of nonstarch polysaccharides (dietary fiber). *Gastroenterology*, 103(6), 1783-1789.
- Dannenber, A. J., Lippman, S. M., Mann, J. R., Subbaramaiah, K., & DuBois, R. N. (2005). Cyclooxygenase-2 and epidermal growth factor receptor: pharmacologic targets for chemoprevention. *Journal of clinical oncology*, 23(2), 254-266.
- Darzynkiewicz, Z. (1990). Differential staining of DNA and RNA in intact cells and isolated cell nuclei with acridine orange. In *Methods in cell biology* (Vol. 33, pp. 285-298). Academic Press.
- Darzynkiewicz, Z., Bruno, S., Del Bino, G., Gorczyca, W., Hotz, M. A., Lassota, P., & Traganos, F. (1992). Features of apoptotic cells measured by flow cytometry. *Cytometry*, 13(8), 795-808.

Dubois, R. N., Abramson, S. B., Crofford, L., Gupta, R. A., Simon, L. S., A. Van De Putte, L. B., Lipsky, P. E. (1998). Cyclooxygenase in biology and disease. *The FASEB journal*, 12(12), 1063-1073

Elstein, K. H., & Zucker, R. M. (1994). Comparison of cellular and nuclear flow cytometric techniques for discriminating apoptotic subpopulations. *Experimental cell research*, 211(2), 322-331.

Ferreira, S. H. (1977). Prostaglandins and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs. In *Prostaglandins and thromboxanes* (pp. 353-361). Springer, Boston, MA.

Flower RJ, Moncada S and Vane JR, Analgesic-antipyretics and anti-inflammatory agents: Drugs employed in the treatment of gout. In: *The Pharmacological Basis of Therapeutics* (Eds. Gilman AG, Goodman LS and Gilman A), 6th Edn, pp. 682-698. Macmillan, New York, 1980

Funk, C. D., & FitzGerald, G. A. (1991). Eicosanoid forming enzyme mRNA in human tissues. Analysis by quantitative polymerase chain reaction. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 266(19), 12508-12513.

Funk, C. D., Funk, L. B., Kennedy, M. E., Pong, A. S., & FitzGerald, G. A. (1991). Human platelet/erythrocyte cell prostaglandin G/H synthase: cDNA cloning, expression, and gene chromosomal assignment. *The FASEB Journal*, 5(9), 2304-2312.

Giardiello, F. M., Hamilton, S. R., Krush, A. J., Piantadosi, S., Hylind, L. M., Celano, P., ... & Offerhaus, G. J. A. (1993). Treatment of colonic and rectal adenomas with sulindac in familial adenomatous polyposis. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 328(18), 1313-1316.

Giovannucci, E., Rimm, E. B., Stampfer, M. J., Colditz, G. A., Ascherio, A., & Willett, W. C. (1994). Aspirin use and the risk for colorectal cancer and adenoma in male health professionals. *Annals of internal medicine*, 121(4), 241-246.

Gridley, G., McLaughlin, J. K., Ekblom, A., Klareskog, L., Adami, H. O., Hacker, D. G., ... & Fraumeni Jr, J. F. (1993). Incidence of cancer among patients with rheumatoid arthritis. *JNCI: Journal of the National Cancer Institute*, 85(4), 307-311.

Grilli, M., Chiu, J. J. S., & Lenardo, M. J. (1993). IMF- κ B and rel: Participants in a multiform transcriptional regulatory system. In *International review of cytology* (Vol. 143, pp. 1-62). Academic Press.

Hanif, R., Pittas, A., Feng, Y., Koutsos, M. I., Qiao, L., Staiano-Coico, L., ... & Rigas, B. (1996). Effects of nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs on proliferation and on induction of apoptosis in colon cancer cells by a prostaglandin-independent pathway. *Biochemical pharmacology*, 52(2), 237-245.

Hassid, A., & Levine, L. (1977). Stimulation of phospholipase activity and prostaglandin biosynthesis by melittin in cell culture and in vivo. *Research communications in chemical pathology and pharmacology*, 18(3), 507-517.

Hial, V. A. L. D. E. M. A. R., De Mello, M. C., Horakova, Z. D. E. N. K. A., & Beaven, M. A. (1977). Antiproliferative activity of anti-inflammatory drugs in two mammalian cell culture lines. *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 202(2), 446-454.

Hla, T., & Neilson, K. (1992). Human cyclooxygenase-2 cDNA. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 89(16), 7384-7388.

Hong, S. L., Polsky-Cynkin, R., & Levine, L. (1976). Stimulation of prostaglandin biosynthesis by vasoactive substances in methylcholanthrene-transformed mouse BALB/3T3. *Journal of Biological Chemistry*, 251(3), 776-780.

Hubbard, W. C., Alley, M. C., McLemore, T. L., & Boyd, M. R. (1991). Fatty acid cyclooxygenase metabolism of arachidonic acid in human tumor cells. In *Eicosanoids and other bioactive lipids in cancer and radiation injury* (pp. 27-32). Springer, Boston, MA.

Humes, J. L., Winter, C. A., Sadowski, S. J., & Kuehl, F. A. (1981). Multiple sites on prostaglandin cyclooxygenase are determinants in the action of nonsteroidal antiinflammatory agents. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 78(4), 2053-2056.

Kopp, E., & Ghosh, S. (1994). Inhibition of NF- κ B by sodium salicylate and aspirin. *Science*, 265(5174), 956-959.

Kune, G. A., Kune, S., & Watson, L. F. (1988). Colorectal cancer risk, chronic illnesses, operations, and medications: case control results from the Melbourne Colorectal Cancer Study. *Cancer research*, 48(15), 4399-4404.

Kune, G. A., Kune, S., & Watson, L. F. (2007). Colorectal cancer risk, chronic illnesses, operations and medications: case-control results from the Melbourne Colorectal Cancer Study. *International journal of epidemiology*, 36(5), 951-957.

Levine, L., (1986). Measurement of arachidonic acid metabolites by radioimmunoassay. In: *Manual of Clinical and Laboratory Immunology* (Eds. Fahey JL, Friedman H and Rose NR), 3rd Edn. American Society for Microbiology, Washington, DC.

Liao, X., Lochhead, P., Nishihara, R., Morikawa, T., Kuchiba, A., Yamauchi, M., ... & Sun, R. (2012). Aspirin use, tumor PIK3CA mutation, and colorectal-cancer survival. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 367(17), 1596-1606.

Moorghen, M., Ince, P., Finney, K. J., Sunter, J. P., Appleton, D. R., & Watson, A. J. (1988). A protective effect of sulindac against chemically-induced primary colonic tumours in mice. *The Journal of pathology*, 156(4), 341-347.

Pollard, M., & Luckert, P. H. (1981). Effect of indomethacin on intestinal tumors induced in rats by the acetate derivative of dimethylnitrosamine. *Science*, 214(4520), 558-559.

Pollard, M., Luckert, P. H., & Schmidt, M. A. (1983). The suppressive effect of piroxicam on autochthonous intestinal tumors in the rat. *Cancer letters*, 21(1), 57-61.

Reddy, B. S., Rao, C. V., Rivenson, A., & Kelloff, G. (1993). Inhibitory effect of aspirin on azoxymethane-induced colon carcinogenesis in F344 rats. *Carcinogenesis*, 14(8), 1493-1497.

Rigas, A. N. A. S. T. A. S. I. A., & Levine, L. A. W. R. E. N. C. E. (1984). Arachidonic acid metabolism by rat liver cells (the C-9 cell line). *Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 231(2), 230-235.

Shiff, S. J., Koutsos, M. I., Qiao, L., & Rigas, B. (1996). Nonsteroidal antiinflammatory drugs inhibit the proliferation of colon adenocarcinoma cells: effects on cell cycle and apoptosis. *Experimental cell research*, 222(1), 179-188.

Shiff, S. J., Qiao, L., Tsai, L. L., & Rigas, B. (1995). Sulindac sulfide, an aspirin-like compound, inhibits proliferation, causes cell cycle quiescence, and induces apoptosis in HT-29 colon adenocarcinoma cells. *The Journal of clinical investigation*, 96(1), 491-503.

Steele, G. D. (1994). The national cancer data base report on colorectal cancer. *Cancer*, 74(7), 1979-1989.

Thun, M. J., Namboodiri, M. M., & Heath Jr, C. W. (1991). Aspirin use and reduced risk of fatal colon cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 325(23), 1593-1596.

Thune, I. N. G. E. R., & Furberg, A. S. (2001). Physical activity and cancer risk: dose-response and cancer, all sites and site-specific. *Medicine and science in sports and exercise*, 33(6 Suppl), S530-50.

Vane J. R., (1971). Inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis as a mechanism of action for the aspirin-like drugs. *Nature*, 231(1), 232-235.

Vane, J. R., & Botting, R. M. (2003). The mechanism of action of aspirin. *Thrombosis research*, 110(5-6), 255-258.

Vargaftig, B. B., & Lefort, J. (1977). Acute hypotension due to carrageenan, arachidonic acid and slow reacting substance C in the rabbit: role of platelets and nature of pharmacological antagonism. *European journal of pharmacology*, 43(2), 125-141.

Waddell, W. R., & Loughry, R. W. (1983). Sulindac for polyposis of the colon. *Journal of surgical oncology*, 24(1), 83-87.

Wyllie, A. H. (1980). Glucocorticoid-induced thymocyte apoptosis is associated with endogenous endonuclease activation. *Nature*, 284(5756), 555.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

© 2020 by the authors. TWASP, NY, USA. Author/authors are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in above pages. This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>)

